

An Analysis of Electoral System in Nepal

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Abstract

This research paper's justification is to examine the different facets of electoral systems used in various nations around the globe and to talk about Nepal's electoral system, which is currently in the process of being implemented in preparation for a federal system. The electoral system and inclusive democracy used in modern politics, the CA polls, and national and local elections are also studied. The subject of elections at various levels in a federal system, where inclusive democracy is once again a topic of national discussion. It attempts to bring up the topic of the election system that will be used in the next elections and formulated using a qualitative paradigm-based descriptive study approach. The information for the study was gathered using both primary and secondary methods. The study used a mixed-methods approach, gathering data from primary and secondary sources. In order to validate findings and provide a wider context, secondary data were sourced from databases, reports, and published literature. Primary data were obtained through surveys and interviews with participants. This combination of first-hand accounts and pre-existing information allowed for a thorough understanding of the research topic. Nepal had to deal with the difficult circumstances of modern politics, the FPTP and List PR models used in the CA elections of 2008 and 2013, as well as the general elections of 2017 and 2022. The electoral systems used around the world are described here, along with their benefits and drawbacks, to provide a clear understanding of which electoral system would be best for a nation like Nepal. The results of the federal and provincial elections, as well as the CA elections in 2008 and 2013, are examined in this paper. After the local, provincial, and federal elections held in 2017 and 2022, it also addresses the reforms that must be made to the FPTP, List PR, and any other electoral system that can be more inclusive and proportionate in Nepal.

Keywords: *democracy, diversified society, electoral system, inclusive representation, representative.*

Abbreviation: AV – Alternative Vote; BV - Block Vote; FPTP – First Past the Post; MMP - Mixed Member Proportional; PBV – Party Block Vote; PR – Proportional Representation; SNTV – Single Non-Transferable Vote; STV – Single Transferable Vote.

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Introduction

In the majority of the nations, democracy is widely regarded as the norm. Some essential components of democracy include equal participation from all citizens, regular elections, gender parity, etc. Global democracy began with a focus on men, but as industrialization spread, women's participation in all spheres of life—including politics and government—gradually increased (Ober, 2008). One of the most

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intricate and challenging ways to demonstrate that a particular system is beneficial for a nation is to examine its electoral system. There are many arguments that demonstrate that no electoral system is ideal for any nation, but we can conclude that no form of government is superior to elected ones. As a result, it is necessary to talk about elections and electoral systems because they are now central to representative democracies. Elections are widely recognized as the democratic process for selecting the representative of the people chosen by the people. Nohlen claims that in a legislative election, which forms the executive branch, the election establishes the procedures by which voters can express their political preferences and, in the event of a tie, how votes can be converted into parliamentary seats. In a political structure where elections are frequently held, the electoral system is crucial. According to Nohlen, the electoral system affects a variety of factors, such as voter behavior and election outcomes.

Over the years, Nepal has undergone a number of political transitions in the service of republic federalism, multiparty democracy, and democracy. Still, the government has not become more stable as a result of these changes. 1951 saw the establishment of democracy in Nepal for the first time. However, it was short-lived, as in 1960 the king toppled it and instituted an autocratic government under the guise of Panchayat democracy. Following that, the nation saw multiple political upheavals, unrest, and a bloody civil war that claimed thousands of lives and caused millions of dollars' worth of economic losses between the first battle for democracy and the most recent constitution. 2015 saw the long-awaited promulgation of Nepal's constitution. It plays a critical role in determining the political preferences and power transfers in any political system. It also establishes the nature and functions of political representation and the party system in a given political and electoral system. In order to establish a precedent for the future, institutionalize democratic norms, and protect the will of the people, the researcher looks for the electoral system that Nepal currently uses or needs to implement. In the name of stable politics, Nepal has seen numerous movements, civil wars, and constitutions over the last eight decades of its political history. The founding of democracy in 1951, the dissolution of the parliament by King Mahendra in 1960 for the purpose of maintaining political stability, the return of democracy in 1990, the Maoist insurgency in 1995, and the comprehensive peace agreement in 2063. These significant political developments promised the establishment of a stable government that would improve the lot of the populace.

Statement of Problem

The purpose of this study is to close the knowledge gap about the electoral processes of 2017 and 2022 by concentrating on the policies and initiatives of mainstream political parties that support just leadership. It is crucial that Nepal's electoral system take into account the various groups of its citizens and ensure that they are fairly represented at all levels, from local to national. It is claimed that the municipal, provincial, and federal elections in 2017 and 2022, as well as the CA polls conducted in 2008 and 2013, are more inclusive, unbiased, free, and fair. This paper attempts to address these important topics. It also clarifies the elements that have helped or hindered marginalized and underprivileged groups' aspirations to hold elected office. Currently, there are some questions to be discussed in this paper.

- a) What are the major tenets of the electoral system in the world?
- b) How is the electoral system practiced in Nepal and what are its strength and weaknesses?

Objectives

This paper is prepared using broad information to examine different electoral systems and make an argument for the most appropriate one given Nepal's electoral practices, which include different electoral systems for federal, provincial, and local elections as well as presidential elections.

The specific objectives of this research are:

- To describe the major tenets of the electoral system in the world
- To analyze the electoral system practiced in Nepal with its strength and weaknesses

Significance of the Study

This paper attempts to examine the theoretical and conceptual underpinnings of the diverse electoral system practices that have been implemented in the world's various nations up to this point. It also makes an effort to highlight the benefits and drawbacks of these systems, pinpoint their successes, and determine which electoral system would work best in a nation like Nepal following discussions of issues, difficulties, case studies of its past experiences, and a diverse society where social divisions overlap among various ethnic groups and communities. Nepal recently adopted a federal system of governance, and in 2017 and 2022 B.S., the country held its first municipal, provincial, and federal elections. The best electoral system for a country like Nepal must be chosen after debating the issues, facing difficulties, and studying case studies of its experiences. It must also take into account the diverse society in which social divisions overlap among various ethnic groups and communities, as well as the advantages and disadvantages of the election systems used in previous CA and general elections. The electoral system required inclusivity.

Literature Review

The importance of constitutional decisions in democracies has been discussed by a wide range of intellectuals, particularly when it comes to choosing an electoral system—majoritarian, proportional, or hybrid—for example. This essay analyzes Nepal's electoral system using ideas from Powell, G. Bingham's *Election as Instrument of Democracy* and Arend Lijphart's *Electoral Systems and Party Systems*. This paper uses Lijphart's (1994) theoretical framework on electoral systems and democracy to analyze Nepal's electoral system through the lens of his majoritarian versus consensus democracies. The electoral landscape that exists in Nepal today combines aspects of consensus and majoritarianism. Both proportional representation and first-past-the-post have been used in the country; each has particular effects on political stability, representation, and governance. In light of this, this essay will critically examine the contributions made by these electoral systems to Nepal's political environment, concentrating on how they affect inclusivity, majority rule, and the efficient operation of the government. By using Powell's theory, which holds that elections are an essential component of democracy, as a starting point. According to his theory, elections are a means of expressing popular will, guaranteeing a peaceful handover of power, and encouraging accountability. Expanding on Powell's observations, this study aims to analyze Nepal's electoral system—both majoritarian and proportional—critically in terms of its effects on inclusiveness, political stability, and efficient governance. This study attempts to evaluate the merits and demerits of Nepal's current electoral system by utilizing Powell's theoretical concepts (Powell, 2000).

A contributor who makes the case for the benefits of the FPTP system is Andrew Heywood. According to him, the FPTP system enables governments to be formed by election results that are determined by the electorate either by a clear mandate or by a plurality of votes. It also gives voters a clear choice of possible parties and executives that can govern. Moreover, Heywood points out that the system creates a strong, functional government because a single party typically holds the majority of assembly seats, which keeps extremism in check by making it harder for small radical parties to obtain political power through assembly seats (Heywood, 208).

In their book "Encyclopedia of Democratic Thought" published in 2003, Paul Berry Clare and Joe Foweraker observe that Western European and Latin American democracies place a great deal of emphasis on list proportional representation (PR). They go on to explain that PR is an electoral system in which voters generally choose one party from a list of contenders displayed on a blank ballot. Voters may also, in certain circumstances, be able to select or rank particular candidates on the list linked to their preferred party. The "highest average method," which divides the parties' vote shares by a number of divisors, is the most widely used technique. The party with the highest average total is awarded a seat at each stage, after which their total is divided once more (Clare & Foweraker, 2003. p. 262).

However, the political process exposes a conflict between the growing disparity in the majority of people's standard of living and the formal rights and statuses expressed in "one person, one vote" and political equality. The fact that the vast majority of people are impoverished demonstrates a divide between extreme idealism and hard cynicism, as well as the painful emptiness of political life. According to Dahal (2017), the institutionalization of familism, elitism, and patrimonialism as ascriptive rights is impeding social transformation and the ability of policy to address issues of poverty, inequality, and dependency.

The election system in Nepal is becoming more costly, according to Nilakantha Uppreti, a former chief electoral commissioner. He claims that openly available audit reports clearly show that the expense of holding the three elections that have been held since 2064 has doubled in subsequent regular elections. He goes on to say that practically all of the elected governments in our past have been unstable, and that the current election system is incapable of bringing about new changes. Without a doubt, the institutional growth of democracy depends on political stability. But there has been a lot of research done on the definition of political stability (Uppreti, 2078).

Methodology

The study employed a descriptive methodology grounded in the qualitative paradigm to prepare the paper. The information for the study was gathered using both primary and secondary methods. In order to get firsthand information directly from participants and provide particular insights into their experiences and perspectives, primary methods like surveys and interviews were employed. By providing established research and relevant trends, secondary methods, on the other hand, involved analyzing already published literature and data, which helped contextualize the findings and provide support for the primary data. Collectively, these techniques improved the study topic's overall analysis and comprehension. Qualitative research is a wealth of data that prioritizes gathering information within philosophical frameworks. The study's selection of Nepal as the research field and the various electoral systems used throughout the world for comparative analysis. utilizing qualitative data collection techniques and a descriptive study design. This study made an effort to concentrate on the practical electoral systems used around the globe and which one would be most appropriate for Nepal.

The study will require the collection of information from books in libraries, the internet, and published materials on related topics from newspapers, books, magazines, and archives on representation, inclusion, and policymaking in political institutions. The information is gathered from reliable and authentic sources, including statistical facts, historical evidence, and data. To investigate real theories and concepts, appropriate websites are consulted, along with relevant external links.

Discussion

Every nation in the world has a different electoral system in place. Every one of these systems has advantages and disadvantages.

The chart given below (Figure 1) shows the electoral system in the world.

The plurality/majority system's basic idea is straightforward. The candidate or the party with the most votes is proclaimed the victor after the votes have been cast and counted. In this way, this system is widely implemented in practice. There are five known varieties of this system.

- a) FPTP (First-Past-The-Post System)
- b) AV (Alternative Vote)
- c) BV (Block Vote)
- d) PBV (Party Block Vote)
- e) TRS (Two Round System)

Figure 1. Plurality / Majority system

First-Past-The-Post System

The most basic type of plurality/majority electoral system, First-Past-the-Post, uses candidate-centered voting and single-member districts. The candidate who receives the most votes overall is proclaimed the victor; however, a candidate may still be elected with just one or two extra votes. FPTP is used by 22% of the global population. This system is used in the UK, Canada, India, Malaysia, Bangladesh, and other nations.

The merits of FPTP system:

- Clear cut choice of voter.
- Allows voters to choose the parties and the persons.
- Excluding the extremist party from representing the legislature.
- Gives rise to single party governance.
- Promotes geographical accountability with the link between constituency and the legislature

The demerits of FPTP system:

- Encourage the political parties based on clan or ethnicity.
- Excludes smaller parties from fair representation.
- Leaves large number of votes wasted.
- Excludes common, minorities from their representation.
- Cause vote splitting. (Nohlen; 36)

India uses the First Past the Post (FPTP) electoral system, which is said to perform best in nations with two main political parties. In India, on the other hand, the Congress Party maintained a steady central

government without a strong challenge from 1952 until 1977. Nevertheless, the National Commission also noted that, in the last three nationwide general elections, FPTP was used to elect an average of two thirds of Indian Members of Parliament without the need for a majority of 50% plus 1. (India case study)

Alternative Vote System

A preferential plurality/majority voting method, the Alternative Vote System is utilized in districts with only one member. Numbers are used by voters to indicate their preferences on the voting paper. A candidate is deemed elected if they obtain a perfect majority of legitimate first-preference votes. Votes are reallocated based on second preferences for the least successful candidates until one wins an absolute majority of first preferences. This process continues until a candidate secures an absolute majority. Australia, Fiji, Papua New Guinea, and Ireland's presidential election are among the nations using this system.

The merits of AV system:

- Supports the candidate who has little hope of winning.
- Advantage of transferring the ballots that enables the votes of several candidates to accumulate.
- Choose the candidate with second preference, not the parties.
- The diverse but related interest can be combined to win representation.
- Can provide significant incentives for accommodating and cooperative politics.

The demerits of AV system:

- Requires a reasonable degree of literacy and numeracy.
- Doesn't work well when applied to larger, multi-member districts.
- Often produce results that are disproportional when compared to PR or FPTP System.
- Promoting centrist outcomes is very dependent on underlying social and demographic conditions. (Nohlen; 49)

Block Vote System

In districts with multiple members, the block vote system is a plurality/majority method. Voters can generally cast their ballots for individual candidates rather than for parties, and they have as many votes as there are seats up for grabs in their districts. Voters are free to cast as many or as few ballots as they like. The seats are awarded to the candidate who receives the most votes overall. This system is used in Kuwait, Laos, Lebanon, Tonga, Palestine, Tuvalu, and other nations.

The merits of BV system:

- Retaining voter's ability to vote for individual.
- Allowing for reasonable sized geographical districts.
- Increasing the role of parties as compared to FPTP system.
- Strengthening those parties which demonstrate most coherence and organizational ability.

The demerits of BV system:

- Have unpredictable and often undesirable impacts of election outcomes.
- Single party may rule.
- The party may win more seats with less percentage of votes.
- Creates severe difficulties for the effective functioning of a parliamentary system (Nohlen; 44).

In Palestine, election reparations started in 1994 concurrently with negotiations, and AV and STV voting systems were adopted. However, the perception of natural boundaries on the ground led to the selection of the BV electoral system, which has districts ranging in size from one in the small towns of Jericho, Salfit, and Tubas to twelve in Gaza City. (Case study- Palestine)

Party Block Vote System

Party block voting is a plurality/majority system that uses multi-member districts. Under this system, voters cast a single, party-centered vote for the party of their choice without making a choice between the candidates. Every seat in the electoral districts is won by the party with the most votes. The winner does not need to receive a clear majority of the votes. By 2004, the main parts of this system were present in Singapore, Djibouti, Cameroon, and Chad.

The merits of PBV system:

- Encourages strong parties.
- Ensures balanced ethnic representation.
- Allows parties to put up mixed slates of candidates for minority representation.
- Enables parties to present ethnically diverse lists of candidates for elections.

The demerits of PBV system:

- May produce highly disproportional results.
- One party wins almost all of the seats.
- Sometimes there is no opposition (Nohlen; 47).

Two Round System

A second round of elections is held in the Plurality/Majority system known as "two rounds," which is activated when no candidate or party receives a certain number of votes, usually an absolute majority (50 %+) in the first round. More than two candidates may run in the second round in a plurality or majority format, but only the top contenders will be allowed to run and the candidate who receives the most votes overall wins the seat. Many countries, including the Congo, Gabon, Mali, Haiti, Iran, Georgia, and Egypt, use this system.

The merits of this system:

- Allows voters to have a second chance to vote for chosen candidates.
- Encourages diverse interest to coalesce behind the successful candidates.
- Lessens the problem of vote splitting.
- Enables voters to make a complete fresh choice in the second round if they desire so.

The demerits of this system:

- Places considerable pressure on the electoral administration.
- Shares more of the disadvantages of FPTP system.
- Implication for deeply divided societies.
- May prompt the opposition to boycott the second round (Nohlen; 53).

Semi Proportional Representation

A system with both plurality/majority and proportional representation is known as semi-proportional representation. Compared to the FPTP system, this one allows voters to vote based on party affiliation, gives them more options, and allows for greater inclusivity.

Two varieties of this system are identified:

- a) Parallel Mixed System
- b) SNTV (Single Non-Transferable Vote)

Parallel Mixed System

The Parallel Mixed System makes use of both PR and Plurality/Majority components; however, in contrast to the MMP system, it does not adjust for disproportionality within the Plurality/Majority districts. Under this hybrid system, representatives are chosen using the votes cast in two separate elections processes: the PR system and the Plurality/Majority system. Many countries, including Senegal, Russia, Armenia, Pakistan, South Korea, Japan, and the Seychelles, use the parallel system.

The merits of Parallel system:

- Usually gives results somewhere between pure Parallel/ Majority and pure PR system.
- Fragments the party system less than a pure PR system.
- Small minority party can be successful to get more winning seats in the proportional allocation.

The demerits of Parallel system:

- Two classes of representatives are created.
- Doesn't guarantee overall proportionality and some parties may shut out of representation.
- It is relatively complex and can leave voters confused as to the nature and operation of the electoral system (Nohlen; 112).

Single Non-Transferable Vote system

In districts with multiple members, voters can cast a single vote under the single non-transferable vote system. The candidates whose total number of votes is highest are proclaimed elected. Though there are multiple seats up for grabs in each electoral district, voters choose the candidate over political parties. Under the SNTV system, political parties may encounter difficulties. Afghanistan, Jordan, Vanuatu, Indonesian second chamber elections, Thailand, etc. all use the SNTV system.

The merits of SNTV:

- Better to facilitate the representation of minority parties and independent candidates.
- Encourages parties to become highly organized and instruct their voters to allocate their votes to candidates.
- Enables a number of popular non-party candidates to be elected.
- This system is praised for being easy to use and understand.

The demerits of SNTV:

- Gives voters only one vote and contains few incentives for political parties.
- Gives rise to many waste votes.
- Multiple candidacies from the same party may lead to fragmentation and discord internally.
- Larger parties can receive a substantial seat as bonus (Nohlen; 113).

Proportional Representation

To implement proportional representation, multiple-number electoral districts must be used. Any PR system is logically based on the deliberate conversion of a party's percentage of votes into a corresponding number of legislative seats. The PR system makes it easier for women, minority groups, and regional fiefdoms to have representation from minority parties. Voter wastage is less likely. Nearly every vote cast in PR elections goes toward electing the candidate of choice when the thresholds are low.

Electing a candidate of choice.

Three varieties of PR system are identified.

- a) List PR (List Proportional Representation)
- b) MMP (Mixed Member Proportional)
- c) STV (Single Transferable Vote)

List Proportional Representation

Every political party or coalition submits a list of candidates for multi-member electoral districts under a list proportional representation system. Parties are given seats based on the total percentage of votes cast by the parties that the electorate supports. The electoral system is not entirely specified by the List PR option; further information needs to be ascertained. Following the vote count, the seats can be distributed using either the Largest Remainder Method (LRM) or the Highest Average (HV) method. Open, closed, and free lists are available. Israel, Turkey, South Africa, the Netherlands, Cambodia, and Belgium are among the nations that use the List PR system.

The merits of List PR system:

- More likely to represent the minority and cultural groups.
- Representation of women and under privileged groups is promoted.
- Ensures that the legislature includes members of both majority and minority groups.
- Parties can be encouraged by the system to craft balanced candidate list.

The demerits of List PR system:

- Weak links between elected legislators and their constituencies.
- Excessive entrenchment of power within party headquarters.
- Need for some kind of recognized party or groups to exist.
- Close lists do not allow voters to determine the identity of candidates (Nohlen; 61-62).

Mixed Member Proportional System

The Mixed Member Proportional System (MMP) aims to achieve the benefits of Proportional Representation. The PR seats are given out to offset any disproportionality resulting from the district seat results. There is only one option available to voters, and the party totals are determined by adding together the totals of each district's contenders. It's a hybrid system where representatives are chosen using the choices made by the electorate in two separate ways: plurality/majority and list PR. Among the nations using the MMP system are Albania, Germany, Lesotho, Mexico, Venezuela, Italy, and New Zealand.

The merits of MMP system:

- Ensures the elected representatives are linked to geographical districts.
- Two votes; one for party and the other for local representatives.

- Creates two classes of legislature.
- This may have implication for the cohesiveness of groups of elected party representatives.

The demerits of MMP system:

- Less preferable than List PR.
- Votes to be wasted in the support of their own candidate.
- Gives rise to strategic voting anomalies.
- Provides candidate sympathy with the National Party's ideas (Nohlen; 95).

The electoral system that was selected in South Africa has also affected the gender and ethnic makeup of the legislature. In May 1994, the South African National Assembly took office. contained more than 80 former members of the white-only parliament, but that was the point at which the two systems diverged. While FPTP would have predicted a polarized form of representation, major political parties favor the PR or MMP system. (Research case: South Africa)

One of the best examples of a nation with a first-past-the-post (FPTP) electoral system used to be New Zealand. However, New Zealand adopted a mixed member proportional (MMP) voting system in a unicameral parliament with 120 members following two referendums in the early 1990s. Three general elections had been conducted under the new system up until the end of 2004. In New Zealand, there are two MMP thresholds. A party must either win at least one single-member district seat or at least 5% of all party votes cast in a general election in order to receive a share of the seats in the parliament based on party votes. (Research case: New Zealand)

Single Transferable Vote System

In a multi-member district, voters rank the candidates using the Single Transferable Vote System, a preferential system. Candidates who receive more first preference votes than a predetermined threshold are elected. A set of counts is used to determine the outcome. The total number of first preference votes cast for each candidate is determined at the first count. A candidate is elected right away if their first preference vote total is higher than or equal to the quota. The extra votes cast for elected candidates are reallocated in accordance with the second preferences listed on the ballot paper in the second and subsequent counts. This system is used in the following countries: Malta, Estonia, Republic of Ireland, Australia, British Columbia, local elections in Scotland, etc.

The merits of STV system:

- Allows the choice between the parties and candidates within parties.
- Final results retain a fair degree of proportionality.
- Provides a better chance for the election of popular independent candidates than List PR.
- Voters can influence the composition of post-election coalitions.

The demerits of STV system:

- It is not suitable in many societies at very least degree of literacy and numeracy.
- Produces pressure to political parties to fragment internally.
- Intricacies of a STV count are quite complex
- Proves to be a little troublesome in practice (Nohlen; 76 – 77).

Besides these electoral systems, other systems are also in practice which is given below.

1. Limited Vote System (LV)

2. A candidate-centered electoral system known as the limited vote system is utilized in multi-member districts where voters have multiple votes but fewer total votes than there are candidates running for office. Seats are awarded to the candidate who receives the most votes. (Nohlen; 117)
3. Cumulative Vote System (CV)
4. Voters in this system are entitled to cast ballots for as many candidates as necessary, based on multi-member constituencies. The ability of voters to split their votes among multiple candidates or focus on just one is one of the system's core features.

The explanation provides a clear picture of electoral systems and their necessity for every nation based on its unique geographic, social, economic, and cultural characteristics. Nepal is a nation with many different cultures, religions, castes, languages, and ethnic groups. They are subjected to various social divisions, some of which overlap. Upon observing these heterogeneous communities, it becomes evident that their customs, traditions, languages, and other aspects of life are distinct and differing. Many of these various caste and ethnic groups are also denied the constitutionally guaranteed rights and face precarious social situations. These groups are underrepresented in all fields because many of them do not have access to health and educational resources. Not even these people are able to show interest, comprehend the significance of the electoral system, and cast their votes. However, in recent times, things have changed, and people now have the ability to choose how they want to be represented in various fields, particularly politics.

In the context of Nepal

Nepal has a lengthy history of using STV elections for assemblies and FPTP elections for the legislature. However, the 2008 Constituent Assembly election brought in the mixed system of PR and FPTP (Mishra, 2008, p. 9). Numerous diverse groups were given the chance to be represented in the constituent assembly by the CA polls. Additionally, it provided women with an opportunity to represent roughly 33% (32.78%) in the CA 1, which was the biggest victory in Nepali election history. The 2008 California Election Act established the procedures for creating a close list of candidates under the PR system and established the proportions of the following groups: Madhesis (31.2%), Dalit (13%), Adibasi Janajati (37.8%), Backward Areas (4%), and Others (30.2%), with women making up 50% of the total. (Dahal, 2009. p. 23). The Janajatis who did not submit their candidacies were Kusunda, Bankaria, Raute, Surel, Hayu, Raji, Koosbadia, Singmama, Thudam, Bote, Bhote, Darai, Tajpuriya, Chhantyal, Fri, Larke, Lepcha, Chayrotan, Tingaule, Thakali, and Kishan. These Janajatis were not selected from the closed list, including Sunuwar, Meche, Dhanuk, Dolpo, Baram, Balunge, Pahari, and Tokpegola. The CA election aimed to promote inclusivity by providing representation to women, Dalits, indigenous groups, Janajati, Madhesi, and the third gender. Despite this, some groups were not given the opportunity to participate in the first CA. Election Commission Report 2064, p. 7, Upreti, 2009.

The two major parties, the CPN-UML and the NC, shared a similar view on mixed elections. Other parties, such as the Nepal Dalit Janajati, Terai Madhesi Loktantrik, Janamorcha, RPP, and RPP Nepal, preferred the FPTP system over the PR system. Therefore, based on population, it was determined that the parallel mixed system (FPTP + PR) was more inclusive for the participation of marginalized, voiceless, and powerless groups of people, such as Adibasi, Janajati, Madhesi, women, Dalit, handicapped, and third gender. The federal system's various election levels are using the same election system. Is it not necessary to talk about the issues and difficulties that the FPTP with PR system faced in the 2017 and 2022 elections?

In the 601-member CA election, FPTP was used to elect 240 candidates, PR was used to elect 335 candidates, and government nominations were used to elect 26 candidates. In the CA 1, twenty-five parties were given the opportunity to be represented. Even though some parties were not given a single seat in the FPTP, they were nevertheless represented by PR. Even though it made significant progress

toward inclusivity in the past, it wasn't proportionately complete. Equal seats in the FPTP and PR systems are required for the nations that use the parallel system.

In the past, Nepal has used the First-Past-The-Post (FPTP) system ever since voting was instituted. However, during the 2008 and 2013 California Assembly elections, the country also used the proportional representation (PR) system. Unfortunately, the proportions of FPTP and PR were switched in the Nepalese constitution, with 60% of seats going to FPTP and 40% to PR. This was the case in both of the CA elections, where 60% of the seats were allotted to PR and 40% to FPTP. 2017 saw the completion of municipal, provincial, and federal elections. Due to two ballot papers, which caused confusion among the uneducated during the election, 5% of votes were deemed invalid—the highest percentage of invalid votes to date—because not all voters are created equal.

A different election system might have produced a different outcome (Upreti, 2009, p. 13). Therefore, in order to address the issues with the Mixed System, there needs to be more national discussion and debate. On November 26, the first phase was implemented in 32 districts located in the mountainous area. A total of 74 provincial assemblies across the provinces and 37 House of Representatives constituencies were up for election. On December 7, the second phase was implemented in 45 Tarai and hill districts. In the second phase, contests were held for 256 provincial assemblies and 128 House of Representatives seats (Himalayan Times, 2074). On November 20, 2022, Nepal's HoR and provincial elections were conducted. Two rounds of elections were held: one for the House of Representatives (HoR) with 275 seats, and another for the provincial assemblies of seven provinces in Nepal with 550 seats. Voters in Nepal are tallied using a mixed system, with 60% of the votes at all levels of government being counted via First Past the Post (FPTP) and 40% through Proportional Representation (PR). Thus, four ballots were distributed to each voter in Nepal.

Conclusion

Nepal requires a modified Parallel Mixed system for its electoral system. The Nepali constitution, which went into effect in 2015 A.D., cleared the way for the country to become federal. In 2017, Nepal held its first federal elections, signaling a significant turning point in the country's transformation into a federal democratic republic and offering greater representation for underrepresented groups, particularly women. In 2022, elections were conducted for all three levels of government. These were the second round of elections at every level since the Nepalese Constitution was adopted in 2015. To ensure that every citizen feels invested in and involved in the process of building their country and establishing federalism in Nepal, there needs to be better preparation for the elections. Since more voters disapproved of the closed list PR system, the electoral system might offer opportunities to fix the errors that occurred in the CA elections. When voters participated in List PR on behalf of the parties, they did not know which candidates they were supporting by name.

The closed list was used in the List PR, and party leaders chose which of their preferred candidates to support in the parliamentary or Constituent Assembly elections, taking over the role of the election commission. Nepal's political past and democratic transition have been tumultuous. We already know that the mixed system can lead to mistakes, so we need to learn how to avoid making the same ones again and adopt a more appropriate electoral system for a nation like Nepal.

A few practical remedial measures can be suggested to the policy makers to remove the existing anomalies and challenges in the field of both electoral systems in Nepal so far.

- Equal percentage of seats for FPTP and PR need to be allocated.
- Election commission needs to get full authority for the List PR to elect the candidate.
- STV system can be preferred for closed list.

- Threshold should be fixed at the minimum margin of 5% like Germany, Russia or New Zealand according to which the parties which fail to secure 5% of the votes nationwide are ineligible to be awarded seats from the PR List.
- System of threshold can reduce the possibilities of splitting the parties and encourage the smaller and weak parties to merge together.

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